

Strelitzia nicolai Natal wild banana

© G.J. Mann

Phylum: Magnoliophyta

Estimated genome size: 739 million DNA base pairs (0.74 Gigabases)
Organism size: 7 to 8 meters in height

Distribution:

The Natal wild banana is native to eastern South Africa, growing in the Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal and further north. It is restricted to the evergreen coastal forests, and thickets.

Importance:

The Natal wild banana is one of the three largest *Strelitzia* species. It produces flowers with white sepals and blue petals. It plays a key ecological role in coastal forests, providing food and shelter for birds and other animals.

PromethION Sequencing Report: Output: 58.71 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 9.69 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome length: 568.92 million bases (0.57 Gigabases)
BUSCO completeness score (single and duplicated genes): 98.8%
[Single: 57.6%, Duplicated: 41.2%]

Sample Contributor contact details

Prof. Eshchar Mizrachi
University of Pretoria
eshchar.mizrachi@fabi.up.ac.za